

ANALYSIS OF BARE FRAME AND INFILLED FRAME BUILDINGS FOR DIFFERENT SEISMIC PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

Strength and stiffness are the main requirements for any structural building. But now a day's bare frames are most common in the all over country. In bare frame design neglecting the masonry loads. Masonry is the most commonly used materials in the buildings. In this paper we study the behavior of bare and infilled frame for OMRF and SMRF in all seismic zones i.e. II, III, IV and V. Comparing the results of story drift and base shear. For problem formulation geometry of the structure is being considered. Variations of height, i.e. (G+4), (G+6), (G+8) & (G+10) for 4x4 bay is modeled in STAAD-PRO V8i. Loads of wall and slabs are being calculated and are assigned to the structures.

KEYWORDS: RC frame, Infill frame, bare frame, SMRF, OMRF, base shear, story drift etc.